

A 6.78 MHz Maximum Efficiency Tracking Active Rectifier with Load Modulation Control for Wireless Power Transfer to Implantable Medical Devices

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Abstract— This paper presents a novel integrated wireless power transfer receiver for implantable medical devices, including a load-modulation feedback loop and an active rectifier with maximum efficiency tracking technique. The feedback loop enables the control of the power delivered to the load by means of a frequency modulation of the receiver load, introducing an efficiency loss of only 1.64 %. The active rectifier maximizes the efficiency of the link through a second feedback calibration loop of the off-transition of the active diodes, showing a Voltage Conversion Ratio of 0.98 and a Power Conversion Efficiency between 0.86 and 0.91 for a wide range of load conditions. The chip was designed in the 180 nm BCD-on-SOI XFAB technology and evaluated with accurate electrical simulations and Monte Carlo runs.

Keywords— *implantable medical devices, wireless power transfer, load modulation, active rectifier*

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration and miniaturization of electronic and mechanical systems is enabling new and more relevant use cases for Implantable Medical Devices (IMDs) in the real-time monitoring of vital parameters. An example of IMD is the untethered endoscopy capsule, used for the monitoring of the gastro-intestinal (GI) tract. It typically includes several sensing systems, from temperature and pH sensors to micro-ultrasound arrays and white light imaging for diagnosis and navigation [1].

The power supply for a complex IMD such as an endoscopic capsule is a serious challenge, due to the demands of the numerous electronic systems on board, the small available volume, and the desired long permanence time in the body. Wireless Power Transfer (WPT), in particular near-field inductive coupling, represents a promising solution to deliver the required power without bulky energy storing systems [2]. The distance of a few tens of cm and the possible misalignment between transmitter (TX) and receiver (RX) coils pose additional challenges and reduce the coupling factor k of the WPT link to $10^{-3} \div 10^{-2}$. Other critical constraints are represented by the maximum Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) and the maximum induced current densities in the body tissues [3,4], which must respect the standard safety specifications.

The WPT system must be designed to minimize power absorption whilst pursuing maximum power efficiency under any condition. Fig.1 shows the block diagram of an inductive WPT system: the inductive link consists of the primary coil L_{TX} , placed outside the patient (typically on a robotic arm used to remotely drive the capsule, or on a wearable belt around the patient), and of the secondary coil L_{RX} on the capsule, with inductive coupling factor $k \ll 1$. Several works have studied the optimum design of the WPT link, in terms

Fig. 1. Generic WPT system lumped elements model in the low-MHz range. Highlighted are the power and efficiency quantities at different points of the circuit.

of coil shape, size and materials [4,5] to maximize the power efficiency and guarantee the sufficient power stability during the inspection of the GI tract. However, this condition can be very hard to meet, considering the intricate path and varying relative position of the capsule with respect of the primary coil: additional feedback techniques to detect the reduction of the power delivered to the load P_{LOAD} and consequently increase the transmitted power are often implemented [6,7]. The receiver side typically includes a matching network (formed by C_S - C_P in Fig.1) to both accomplish the resonance with L_{RX} at the link frequency and at the same time adapt the output voltage of the WPT link to the input voltage range of the rectifier [2]. The ac-dc converters typically employed for these applications are CMOS Active Rectifiers, adopting adaptive compensation techniques to maximize the Power Conversion Efficiency (PCE) [7-11].

In this work, we propose the design of a WPT receiver integrated circuit composed of: 1) a load-modulation feedback block for power control based on frequency modulation of the receiver load; 2) an active rectifier implementing a novel Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) technique, with the twofold aims of minimizing the power P_{BODY} ultimately absorbed in the body and maximizing the power efficiency of the WPT system under varying load conditions. The circuit has been designed using the 180 nm BCD-on-SOI XFAB technology.

II. CHALLENGES FOR EFFICIENT WPT

Modeling the presence of the human body between transmitter and capsule depends on the operating frequency. In this work, we choose to operate in the ISM band at 6.78 MHz, as a trade-off between higher k and lower P_{BODY} for a given P_{LOAD} (both k and P_{BODY} increase with increasing f). In this frequency range, a realistic model for the WPT link in the human body is shown in Fig. 1, where parallel and series parasitic lumped resistances have been added both at the transmitter (TX) and the receiver (RX), to model the effects of the propagation loss in the body and resistive loss in the coils, respectively [12]. The parasitic capacitances can

typically be neglected with respect to the resonating capacitances C_{TX} and C_{RX} (resulting capacitance of the matching network).

In the condition of loose coupling ($k \ll 1$), minimizing P_{BODY} becomes of vital importance in order to comply with SAR limitations, which must be met under any conditions. In particular, the quantity $\eta_{BODY} = P_{LOAD}/P_{BODY}$ has to be maximized for any desired P_{LOAD} , so that only the amount of power necessary for the correct operation of the load is introduced in the body. Since we can only control the value of the total efficiency η , we can rewrite its expression as a function of the quantities shown in Fig. 1:

$$\eta = \frac{P_{LOAD}}{P_{IN}} = \eta_{BODY} \frac{P_{BODY}}{P_{IN}} = PCE \eta_{LINK} \frac{P_{BODY}}{P_{IN}}, \quad (1)$$

where $PCE = P_{LOAD}/P_{RECT}$ is the power conversion efficiency of the rectifier and $\eta_{LINK} = P_{RECT}/P_{BODY}$ is the link efficiency. The quantity P_{BODY}/P_{IN} can be considered almost independent of what happens on the RX side when $k \ll 1$, because the RX has almost no effect on the TX side, therefore maximizing η_{BODY} coincides with maximizing η .

Typical WPT systems [8-11] are designed with the goal of achieving the maximum PCE, with no consideration of η_{LINK} . On the other hand, it is known that, for such loosely coupled links, the maximum link efficiency is achieved when the effective input resistance of the matching network R_{MN} matches the equivalent link output resistance at the RX side R_{RX} . The matching condition $R_{MN} = R_{RX}$ ensures working at both the Maximum Efficiency and Maximum Power Point (MEP and MPP, respectively). Let us stress that this property does not apply for high k ($> 10^{-2}$) – where MEP and MPP are reached under different load conditions [2].

A single matching network could optimize η_{LINK} only around a single value of the load, since adapting the matching network to a change of the load would not be feasible due to area limitations and large variations of load conditions.

Our proposed rectifier employs a MPPT approach with the aim of maximizing the overall link efficiency η_{LINK} by means of a modulation of the resistance R_{MN} .

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Fig. 2(a) shows the overall architecture of the proposed WPT system, including the active rectifier implementing MPPT and the load-modulation feedback (LMF) block, which represent the novel contributions of this work.

The LMF block shown in Fig. 2(b) detects the variation of the rectifier output voltage V_{rect} and produces an ad-hoc frequency modulation of the matching impedance on the receiver side. A partition of V_{rect} is compared with two thresholds, V_H and V_L ; depending on the results of these comparisons, one out of three different frequencies of an on-chip relaxation oscillator is selected. The generated clock signal is used to drive the nMOS switch M_{mod} , which implements the modulation of the matching network impedance by connecting/disconnecting the capacitor C_{mod} . The proper driving of M_{mod} is made possible by a bootstrapped driver that guarantees the correct turn-on and turn-off of the transistor. The value of C_{mod} is set at 20 pF, chosen according to a trade-off between a robust detection of the modulated signal on the current of the primary side – by means of a shunt resistor (large C_{mod}), and a negligible effect on the efficiency of the link – by altering the RX resonance (small C_{mod}). Depending on the modulation frequency detected on the primary side, the power amplifier is properly tuned to increment or reduce the transmitted power, as shown in the top-left side of Fig. 2(a).

The full-wave active rectifier nMOS active diodes M_{NP} and M_{NN} are driven with two different feedback loops to calibrate the on-time and off-time delays of the two comparators. The on-time calibration loop is similar to [9], where a switched-capacitor loop generates the proper offset needed to compensate the on-delay of the comparator, achieving the zero-crossing turning-on of M_{NP} , M_{NN} . On the other side, the off-time calibration loop does not pursue optimum zero-crossing, but implements MPPT, by means of the MPPT Control Delay Loop and the Controlled Delay Line (CDL) depicted in Fig.3. The MPPT Control Delay Loop is composed of a continuous-time Power Evaluation block and by a discrete-time PWM Delay Control block, which generates the digital signals for the CDL. The Power Evaluation block is similar to the I - V converter in [9]: using

Fig. 2. Circuitual implementation of the proposed WPT RX chip. (a) Overall system architecture composed of the active rectifier with MPPT (green) and Load Modulation Feedback (orange); the system-level diagram of the TX performing synchronous demodulation is shown in yellow; (b) detail of the multi-frequency relaxation oscillator and bootstrapped driver circuit for the LMF block.

Fig. 3. Architecture of the MPPT control loop, with detail of the Power Evaluation, PWM Delay Control and CDL blocks.

a properly scaled replica (500:1) of the cross-coupled pMOS M_{FP} - M_{FN} , an error amplifier and a pass transistor, the output voltage V_{FB} results proportional to the average value of the current delivered to the load. V_{FB} is periodically sampled with a sampling frequency much lower than the power transfer frequency, generated by an on-chip relaxation oscillator (300 kHz). The result of the sampling operation at the i -th cycle $V_{FB}^{(i)}$ is compared with its value at the previous period $V_{FB}^{(i-1)}$ using a latched comparator. The result of the comparison is needed to update the state of a 5-bit up/down counter: if $V_{FB}^{(i)} > V_{FB}^{(i-1)}$, the counter keeps counting in the same direction as in the previous clock cycle; otherwise, the counting direction is reversed. This signal is given as input to the capacitive 5-bit DAC used to set the delay value of the CDL, which sets the turning-off time of M_{NP} and M_{NN} .

The basic principle of the MPPT Control Delay Loop is the following: let us consider an increase of the turn-off delay set by CDL. If the new V_{FB} sampled after the CDL update is larger than the previous one, it means that the output current of the rectifier has increased, i.e. a larger power is delivered to the load. Thus, the CDL will be updated to keep increasing the turn-off delay. Otherwise, if the new V_{FB} sample has decreased, the CDL will be updated in the opposite direction (reducing the turn-off delay). After an initial transient, the value of the CDL delay will settle around an optimum value that guarantees the maximum power delivered to the load. For different loading conditions, a different CDL delay will be set in order to track the maximum power point, thus the MPPT.

Fig. 4 shows the final layout of the block, with highlight of the various subsystem and a size of $1200 \times 800 \mu\text{m}^2$.

IV. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

The performance of the proposed system was assessed with simulations under different operating conditions and Monte Carlo (MC) analysis, performed with the Cadence Spectre simulator.

Fig. 5(a) shows waveforms of three significant signals (V_{rect} , the TX current I_{TX} and the modulating signal V_{osc}) which best describe the operating principle of the LMF block, tested with variations of the coupling coefficient k so that the rectifier output voltage V_{rect} is inside, below or above the range imposed by the two thresholds (here at 3.6 and 3.8 V). When V_{rect} is inside the threshold limits, the LMF block generates a 35 kHz oscillation, reflected in the envelope of I_{TX} , that will be detected at the primary when flowing through the shunt resistor. When the rectifier voltage exceeds the

Fig. 4. Final layout of the proposed RX chip with MPPT and LMF.

limits, the LMF block responds with oscillations at 15 kHz (V_{rect} below limits) and 55 kHz (V_{rect} above limits), which are again correctly revealed at the TX side. Note that the I_{TX} curve oscillates at the operating frequency of 6.78 MHz and the rectified voltage still presents the typical residual ripple at the same frequency. It also exhibits the oscillation resulting from the modulation. Fig. 5(b) and (c) display the spread of the modulating frequencies and the efficiency loss ($\%_{loss}$) evaluated with 50 MC runs. The $\%_{loss}$ is defined as the percentage of the overall link efficiency with LMF with respect to its value without, with the constraint of correct detection of the modulation at the TX side. The analysis shows a standard deviation of the oscillating frequencies lower than 5% of their mean value; the average $\%_{loss}$ is 1.64%, with a standard deviation of 0.81%, almost negligible.

Fig. 6(a) shows the transient simulation of the output voltage V_{rect} of the proposed active rectifier with MPPT, compared with the corresponding V_{rect} of an ideal rectifier, which performs optimum zero-crossing driving of the diodes, although without a matching network to adapt the load. The two curves are taken under the same conditions: first the same input voltage (V_{in} at the TX side) is applied, with the RX loaded at 100 Ω; then, the load is changed to 150 Ω with a different input voltage to ensure that the V_{rect} level remains almost constant (emulating the effect of the LMF block on

Fig. 5. Performance of the LMF block: (a) simulated waveforms of the various signals when varying the load; Monte Carlo simulations (50 runs) for (b) modulation frequency and (c) efficiency loss ($\%_{loss}$) of the block.

Fig. 6. Performance of the active rectifier with MPPT. (a) output voltage V_{rect} when varying the load; (b) detail of the PWM control signal V_{GP} .

Fig. 7. Evaluation of the (a) output voltage, (b) VCR, (c) PCE and (d) Efficiency Gain of the MPPT rectifier over 50 MC runs, $R_L = 100 \Omega$.

the RX side). The higher V_{rect} level achieved by the MPPT rectifier translates in a higher efficiency under the same conditions: Fig. 6(b) highlights the MPPT principle, in which the driving signal V_{GP} (and, of course, V_{GN}) does not turn-off M_{GP} (or M_{GN}) at the zero-crossing of V_{ACP} (V_{ACN}), but is controlled by the MPPT Control Delay Loop that ensures maximum power tracking. The robustness of the rectifier is evaluated through a MC analysis performed for a fixed load of 100Ω (Fig. 7). It is interesting to have a deeper look at the values of the Voltage Conversion Ratio (VCR) and PCE, in Fig. 7(b) and (c), respectively. The VCR mean value of 0.98 is in line with state-of-the-art solutions; on the other side, a value of 0.89 for the mean of the PCE is actually lower than other proposed rectifiers [9]: this is indeed a result of the MPPT approach, that degrades the power efficiency of the rectifier as a standalone block but enhances the overall efficiency of the link. This is certified by the value of the Efficiency Gain (EG) in Fig. 7(d), defined as:

$$EG = 100 \cdot \frac{\eta_{LINK}^{MPPT} - \eta_{LINK}^{ID}}{\eta_{LINK}^{ID}}, \quad (2)$$

where η_{LINK}^{MPPT} is the link efficiency of the proposed rectifier, and η_{LINK}^{ID} is the one of the ideal rectifier performing optimum zero-crossing. The resulting mean and standard deviation for the EG are of 14.8% and 0.61%.

The system is then evaluated under load variations (from 50 to 300Ω at a fixed V_{rect} of 3.7 V). Fig. 8(a) shows a comparison of the value of P_{rect} (power at the rectifier input) between the proposed rectifier and the ideal one: we see how the MPPT ensures higher levels of power and better link efficiency up until $R_L = 250 \Omega$, as confirmed by Fig. 8(b),

Fig. 8. Performance of the MPPT rectifier over a $50 \div 300 \Omega$ range of load: (a) input power P_{rect} and (b) EG of the rectifier compared with the ideal case; (c) PCE of the proposed MPPT rectifier.

where high values of EG (up to $\sim 20\%$) are reached for several points of the curve. Finally, Fig. 8(c) shows the PCE of the rectifier for the same load range, with a minimum value of 0.86 for $R_L = 50 \Omega$ and a maximum of 0.91 for $R_L = 200 \Omega$.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We have proposed a novel approach for WPT in loosely coupled links aiming at maximum efficiency tracking. Our designed RX chip performs MPPT through PWM driving of the active diodes of the rectifier, with additional load-modulation feedback loop for body loss minimization. Simulations and MC analysis show increased link efficiency for different load conditions, while maintaining high VCR and PCE.

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